

THE BENEFITS OF PSYCHEDELIC THERAPY FOR MENTAL
HEALTH: EXPLORING PSYCHEDELICS

by

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The Benefits of Psychedelic Therapy for Mental Health: Exploring Psychedelics

The usage of psychedelics has been around for centuries in cultures across the world. Many psychedelics are from plant extraction, such as psilocybin and ayahuasca, and are used for social and ceremonial practices. Although psychedelics have widely been used across many cultures, it was not integrated into Western science until the late 1890s. Albert Hofmann's discovery of LSD in 1943 was the real breakthrough for psychedelics, and Hoffman also discovered the psychedelic component of psilocybin, also known as magic mushrooms (Nutt, 2019). Research about these substances flourished during this period but was ultimately hindered when the 1970 ban was put into action. Since then, research has halted; however, within the last 20 years, new research has resurfaced regarding psychedelics and their positive effects on the brain.

When identifying a substance as a psychedelic, there are four categories: classical, empathogens or entactogens, dissociative anesthetic agents, and atypical hallucinogens (Reiff, Richman, Nemeroff, Carpenter, Widge, Rodriguez, Kalin, & McDonald, 2020). For this review, the three psychedelics that were analyzed were psilocybin, ayahuasca, and MDMA. Psilocybin and ayahuasca are considered classical psychedelics because they are plant derived, while MDMA is an empathogen-entactogen. These three psychedelics were analyzed in various studies and their effects on the brain during a psychedelic therapy session were examined. The basis of this review was to understand how beneficial psychedelic therapy can be for those struggling with mental health issues, specifically anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). This research can also be used to understand how psychedelic therapy can potentially be an alternate route for those who failed trials with medication, as well as being a more holistic approach to psychiatry (Donovan, 2022; Carhart-Harris & Goodwin, 2017).

Psychedelic Therapy

Background

Since the 1950s, psychedelic therapy was utilized as a technique to better understand the unconscious of patients. It was a way for psychiatrists to gain better insight of a patient's condition (Reiff et al., 2020). Current research, within the last 20 years, revisited this concept of psychedelic therapy, and explored how it can positively affect those with mental health issues. When this type of therapy is used, the psychiatrist has the patient in a calm and controlled environment. The psychiatrist educates the patient about what to expect for the psychedelic session, as well as gain therapeutic trust. They will then administer a dose of a psychedelic, which allows the patient to have their "trip" experience. During this trip, the psychiatrist supervises the patient to ensure they always feel safe, and only interjects if needed. Once the patient is done, they will explain their experiences to the psychiatrist, and the psychiatrist analyzes these experiences using various integrative therapy techniques (Reiff et al., 2020).

During a patient's psychedelic trip, they can also experience a phenomenon called ego dissolution or ego death. Ego dissolution is the concept of completely losing one's subjective self-identity. It is also described as the blurring of self-representation and object-representation, allowing one to feel unity with their surroundings (Nour, Evans, Nutt, & Carhart-Harris, 2016). The feeling of unity with one's environment correlates to ego-boundaries being disturbed, which results in ego dissolution (Nour et al., 2016). When patients experience ego dissolution, it allows them to feel an out-of-body transcendence, where they can view themselves outside of their bodies. The sense of oneness with the environment and losing subjective self-identity allows patients to rediscover themselves and have a better outlook on life (Nutt, 2019). Overall, the experiences produced by psychedelic therapy are used to have a better understanding of a

patient's condition, create a space for patients to rediscover themselves, and provide a different holistic approach to psychiatry.

Psychedelic Drugs

Psilocybin

A popular psychedelic that has been used for millennia in cultures across the world is psilocybin, also known as magic mushrooms (Nutt, 2019). Psilocybin is described as a hallucinogenic plant alkaloid found in a variety of mushroom species (Reiff et al., 2020). This type of psychedelic drug is considered a classical psychedelic because it is plant derived, and it is ingested orally. Psilocybin, along with other classical psychedelics, is known to have agonistic activity at the serotonin 2A receptor, 5-HT_{2A} (Tupper, Wood, & Johnson, 2015). This agonistic activity means that psilocybin is chemically structured the same as the neurotransmitter serotonin, which allows for psilocybin to bind to the serotonin 2A receptor, creating a similar, yet more enhanced effect on the brain compared to serotonin. Research has analyzed the agonistic activity of psilocybin and have determined its effect on assisting those with severe anxiety and depression disorders.

One such pilot study that supports this claim is by researchers Carhart-Harris et al. (2016). These researchers analyzed the effects of psilocybin on individuals with major depressive disorder by analyzing their depressive symptoms after the administration of the drug. The study consisted of 20 patients who were moderately to severely depressed and had failed trials with other antidepressant treatments. Before patients were administered the psychedelic, it was confirmed that no medication, specifically antidepressants, were in the patients' systems because the medication can block the effects of psilocybin. Once it was confirmed that no medication was present in their bodies, patients were administered two different doses, one 10-

mg “test” and one 25-mg treatment dose. The treatments were administered one week apart, and psychological support was available before and after treatment. Researchers followed up with patients 6 months after the treatment with a QIDS-SR, a depressive symptoms rating scale. Results showed a significant decrease in depressive symptoms with a maximal significance of effect at 5 weeks. These results were significant because they allowed the researchers to determine that psilocybin had a positive effect on the patients. The results also established feasibility and evidence of safety when administering psilocybin. Although researchers noted that efficacy of the study was limited to do the open-label design, positive results were seen with decreasing depressive symptoms.

Another study that supports the claims of psilocybin helping with anxiety and depression was a study conducted by researchers Grob et al. (2011). In this study, researchers focused on psilocybin treatment for terminally ill patients suffering from anxiety. There were 12 patients, 11 of them being women, who were diagnosed with advanced-stage cancer and suffered from anxiety disorder. Patients were given 0.2 mg/kg of psilocybin, which is considered to be a moderate dose, and 250 mg of niacin, an active placebo. This was a double-blind study, so both the administrators and the patients did not know which treatment was being given. After the treatment, there was a 3-month follow up with various anxiety rating scales. Results showed improved mood of patients 2 weeks after treatment, as well as sustained improvement of mood up to 6 months post-treatment. Although there was an effect, there was no significant trends seen. This could be due to many of the patients dying from their cancers, so data was limited. A small dose of psilocybin was administered; therefore, the dosage could have also influenced the results. Regardless of the data, this study was significant because it allowed the researchers to determine a safe dosage to administer to patients and optimize safety. This study allowed

researchers to establish a strong foundation for future research to conduct similar studies regarding terminally ill patients with anxiety or depression disorders. Ensuring the safety of psilocybin was the main goal of this study, and the researchers were able to determine that with their data.

Ayahuasca

The use of ayahuasca has been around for hundreds of years, specifically in South America, for ritualistic, spiritual, and personal practices. Ayahuasca is a decoction of plants *Banisteriopsis caapi* and *Psychotria viridis*, which are plants native to the Amazon basin (Reiff et al., 2020). A decoction is the liquid that comes from the two plants being boiled, and this liquid is ingested orally. Ayahuasca is considered a classical psychedelic because it is plant derived. This psychedelic contains DMT, which, similarly to psilocybin, affects the 5-HT receptors, specifically 5-HT_{1A}, 5-HT_{2A}, 5-HT_{2C}, and 5-HT_{2B} (Reiff et al., 2020). Ayahuasca also has agonistic activity, meaning its chemical structure is similar to the neurotransmitter serotonin, allowing it to bind to the serotonin receptors, creating a similar, yet more enhanced effect on the brain. The active chemical DMT in ayahuasca affects the brain's electrical activity by suppressing alpha waves, which are present when we are awake, and slightly increasing theta waves, which are present when we are dreaming (Timmerman et al., 2019). Various studies show promising preliminary results for the treatment of depression using ayahuasca.

One such study that supports this claim is a study conducted by Brazilian researchers Osório et al. (2015). In this study, there were 6 participants who were clinically depressed and had failed rounds of antidepressant medication. Patients were sent to a psychiatric unit for 2 weeks for a medication washout, and after the 2 weeks, ayahuasca treatment began. Patients drank a standard ayahuasca dose, which was 2.2 mL/kg. Two depression rating scales, HAM-D

and MADRS, were administered at specific time intervals before and after ayahuasca treatment. The scales were administered 10 minutes before treatment and 40, 80, 140, and 180 minutes after treatment. Researchers also administered follow-up assessments 1, 7, 14, and 21 days after ayahuasca treatment. Results for the mean HAM-D scores were reduced by 62% 1 day and 72% 7 days after drug administration, and mean MADRS scores were reduced by 82% 7 days after drug administration. Continued effects of the ayahuasca treatment, according to the MADRS scores, were seen at 21 days. These results were significant because it allowed the researchers to determine that ayahuasca treatment had a significant effect on depressive symptoms of the participants. This study also exhibited the safety of this drug since no adverse effects were seen. Although there were participants who vomited from the ayahuasca treatment, participants reported an overall pleasant experience with ayahuasca. A similar study was conducted by the same researchers with a larger sample size (n=17), and similar positive results were seen.

Although the research conducted by Osório et al. (2015) is considered a pilot study for understanding ayahuasca and its effects on depression disorders, there is still a lack of research about the specifics of this topic. The clinical use of ayahuasca is limited, especially since ayahuasca is known to be used for ceremonial practices (Reiff et al., 2020). Not only is research of ayahuasca in a clinical study limited, but there is also a lack of knowledge of what the specific ingredients of the decoction are, especially since various compounds are integrated into indigenous preparations (Reiff et al., 2020). This can include compounds such as caffeine, nicotine, cocaine, and scopolamine (Reiff et al., 2020). Therefore, more research must be conducted to truly examine the effects ayahuasca has on the brain, specifically with major depressive disorders. The importance of understanding the psychedelic effects of this drug is

crucial, and it is urged that more research is conducted to examine the therapeutic potentials of ayahuasca.

MDMA

MDMA (3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine), which is also known as ecstasy or molly, has received the reputation as a rave or party drug. Although it has been known to be used for recreational purposes, its potential therapeutic effects have widely been analyzed (Nutt, 2019). It is a synthesized drug that is structurally similar to amphetamine or mescaline, and it is considered an empathogen-entactogen (Reiff et al., 2020). As an empathogen-entactogen, this means that MDMA “produces experiences of emotional communion, oneness, relatedness, and emotional openness, such as empathy or sympathy” (“Empathogen-Entactogen,” 2022). MDMA affects the brain by binding to the 5-HT_{1A} and 5-HT_{1B} receptors, causing a decrease in depressive and anxiety symptoms, as well as an increase in positive mood (Sessa, 2017). MDMA has fear-reducing effects, and these effects can potentially “be used to facilitate imaginal exposure, cognitive restructuring, and corrective attachment” (Krediet, Bostoen, Breeksema, van Schagen, Passie, & Vermetten, 2020). Various studies show that the effects of MDMA can be helpful to those struggling with Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) and has potential therapeutic effects.

One such study that supports this statement is a study conducted by researchers Mithoefer et al. (2010), where they examined 20 patients with chronic PTSD. Twelve patients were administered MDMA treatment, while 8 patients were administered an inactive placebo. The treatment was administered during two experimental psychotherapy sessions, which were each 8 hours long. Both groups received preparatory and follow-up psychotherapy without drug treatment and were also administered a Clinical-Administered PTSD scale. The PTSD scale was

administered before treatment, 4 days after treatment, and 2 months after the second session of treatment. Results showed that the PTSD scale scores for the MDMA group were significantly decreased compared to the “before treatment” scores. The MDMA PTSD scale scores were also significantly lower compared to the placebo group. Researchers saw that 85% of the patients no longer had PTSD after one session with MDMA-assisted psychotherapy, and one session consisted of a 16-week course. The same research team followed up with a long-term study, and the results showed that patients no longer needed MDMA intervention. It was also seen that the original results of patients being PTSD free continued 4 years later. These results were significant because it allowed the researchers to determine that MDMA-assisted psychotherapy exhibits positive effects with helping those with chronic PTSD. The long-term effects of MDMA are crucial for understanding the potential therapeutic effects of this type of psychedelic therapy on patients with PTSD.

Another study that analyzes the effects of MDMA on patients with chronic PTSD is one by researchers Wagner et al. (2017). Researchers examined patients (n=20; 17 females, 3 males) who suffered from chronic PTSD, which resulted from crime or war. A personality measure (NEO PI-R) was administered to investigate factors of Neuroticism and Openness. A PTSD symptom measure (CAPS) was utilized to determine whether the patient met the criteria for PTSD diagnosis. The study was conducted as randomized, where some patients had two experimental sessions with MDMA-assisted psychotherapy or with an inactive placebo psychotherapy. Data was gathered before treatment and 2 months after treatment, and there was also a long-term follow up. Results showed that the PTSD scale scores were lower for the MDMA treatment group compared to the placebo group. Researchers also noted that psychotherapy with MDMA treatment influenced personality change, which is associated with

improvement in PTSD symptoms. These results allowed the researchers to determine that treatment with MDMA in a psychedelic therapy setting has significant positive effects on chronic PTSD symptoms. It is reported that PTSD symptoms are decreased significantly during MDMA-assisted psychotherapy compared to a placebo group. These findings create a strong foundation for future research to explore the therapeutic potential of MDMA.

Conclusion

Limitations of Existing Research

Research on psychedelic therapy is compelling; however, there are limitations with existing research. Due to the illegalization of psychedelic drugs in the 1970s, there is a lack of research, as well as a lack of resources, for this topic. Research was halted, and although research on psychedelics is more prevalent, especially within the last 20 years, there is still a lack of research on this topic. Research especially lacks with discussing the therapeutic potential of ayahuasca in a clinical setting; therefore, information on the substance is limited, and it is difficult to determine the true effects of ayahuasca. There is more research on psilocybin and MDMA, which is promising, but there are still unknowns, and it is important to continue research on this topic to understand the long-term effects of these drugs paired with psychedelic therapy.

Another limitation includes the type of study. There are various studies that are open-label designs, meaning both the person administering the drug and the person receiving the drug are aware of what is being administered. This can create potential placebo effects because the participant is expecting the drug to have an effect, which can influence the results (Nutt, 2019). Many studies also have smaller sample sizes, so it is important that larger sample sizes are incorporated into future studies to determine the effects on a larger scale. This data will in turn

allow researchers to gauge the effects on the rest of the population. There is also the risk of worsening the psychosis of the patient because the mechanics of the brain are being tampered with when utilizing psychedelic therapy (Nutt, 2019). Therefore, it is important for researchers to be selective with the disorders they choose for these studies. For example, it is advised that researchers avoid bipolar depression because psychedelic therapy could elicit mania, which would be contradictory to the intended effects of psychedelic therapy (Nutt, 2019). With more studies, researchers can determine which disorders work best with this method of therapy, compared to others that do not.

Although existing research shows it is safe to administer these psychedelic drugs to patients, more research must be conducted to ensure the safety of these drugs. Long-term research is crucial for analyzing the long-term effects of these drugs, as well as ensuring they are safe to administer. There is also the issue of medication blocking the effects of certain psychedelics, such as psilocybin blocked by antidepressants. Therefore, it is crucial that future research ensures that patients participate in a washout to cleanse themselves of any medications that can possibly interfere with the psychedelic they have ingested. Lastly, and most importantly, a major limitation of existing, and future, research is the stigmatization of psychedelics. Most of the public understand how psychedelic drugs can potentially be harmful, but much of their knowledge is ascertained from situations where patients used psychedelics in “unsupervised nonmedical contexts” (Tupper, Wood, & Johnson, 2015). Therefore, it is important to educate the public about the therapeutic potentials of psychedelics, specifically in a controlled, clinical environment. Informing people of the process of psychedelic therapy will allow for a better understanding of the process and how psychedelics can potentially be beneficial for those struggling with mental health issues.

Directions for Future Research

It is important to research the therapeutic benefits of psychedelic therapy because much of current research exhibit promising results for psychedelic use in a clinical setting.

Psychedelic therapy must be explored further to understand its beneficial qualities for those struggling with mental health issues. In order for future research to thrive, it is crucial that individuals are educated about the subject, which in turn will allow for the destigmatization of utilizing psychedelic drugs in a clinical setting. It is also important that more funding is involved to allow for larger studies to occur. Having the support of large companies, such as the FDA, will perpetuate studies about this topic, allowing for more promising research and discoveries.

Lastly, it is important that research continues to further the understanding of the brain and its functions. The brain is complex; therefore, research can be daunting and difficult. However, psychedelic therapy can potentially be the gateway to understanding the mechanics of the brain better. Psychedelics allow researchers to dive deeper into the unconscious mind, and holistic practices can potentially be the answer to certain scientific questions. Having a more holistic approach to mental health introduces a different dynamic to psychiatry, and it is possible, with the help of future research, that pending questions can be answered by unraveling the world of psychedelics.

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